

Co-Design of co-creative methods for identifying care innovations with parental caregivers to enhance quality of life

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Parents of children with increased support needs due to chronic illnesses or disabilities often must navigate daily challenges without the aid of professional services. In response, they develop creative solutions—or care innovations as self-organised carers (Duncon et al. 2019). These parents are experts in their unique life and care situations, albeit often unaware of their own competence and resourcefulness. Recognising their ability to devise and manage creative solutions for everyday challenges can enhance their self-efficacy, which is correlated with both the health and quality of life of the parents and children (Fang et al. 2021).

We aim to collaboratively develop co-creative methods (Curedale 2013, Stickdorn & Schneider 2013) and serious games (Damaševičius et al. 2023) with parental caregivers. These tools are intended to support the identification of the parents' creative solutions to everyday challenges in living with their children. These methods hold the potential to effectively support other family caregivers, such as those caring for elderly adults, in self-help settings. These methods will be further evaluated in a subsequent intervention study regarding their impact on quality of life.

The participatory development of these methods is carried out through an iterative process involving open feedback sessions, field notes, and semi-structured evaluations. As a result, we present the co-creative methods and serious games designed to identify care innovations with parents. These can be applied in self-help and moderated peer-group contexts. Concurrently developed support materials and facilitation guides promote a low-threshold and sustainable implementation by self-organised carers.